

ELF Diacritic Notation – A Practical System Supporting Intelligible English Pronunciation for Non-native Users while Preserving Standard Spelling

Zbigniew Stachowicz, Independent researcher,

e-mail: zrstachowicz@gmail.com , ORCID: 0000-0003-2272-1514

Abstract

This article introduces a novel diacritic-based system for marking English pronunciation without altering standard orthography. The system preserves full compatibility with standard written English. The goal of the proposed ELF Diacritic Notation is to provide pronunciation guidance sufficient for international communication, taking into account the principles of English as a Lingua Franca (ELF), particularly the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). It is intended primarily for communication among non-native speakers, supporting intelligible reading and clear pronunciation while helping readers avoid automatic first-language habits and guiding them toward appropriate English sound production.

The system is also suitable for learners and is particularly well suited to independent learners in its extended version, as it can present both spelling and pronunciation in a unified “two-in-one” format. This dual-function notation guides articulation while reinforcing spelling patterns, making it a practical tool for self-study materials and pedagogical texts.

The article provides detailed rules for the notation and includes comprehensive guidelines and illustrative examples, demonstrating that the proposed system is both feasible and useful. An example of the practical use of this notation is the summary of this article, which is written using diacritical marks.

Keywords: English as a Lingua Franca; ELF; intelligibility; English pronunciation; orthography; diacritics; spelling–pronunciation relationship.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Concept

The spelling of English, unlike that of most other languages written in the Latin alphabet, is characterized by the absence of diacritical marks and consistent rules linking spelling to pronunciation. Dictionaries commonly use a complex system of IPA-based pronunciation symbols, requiring learners to master spelling and pronunciation separately. As a result, many students struggle with correct spelling or articulation, depending on whether they rely more on visual or auditory memory.

Most languages written in the Latin alphabet, such as German, Spanish, French, and author’s native language, Polish, use spelling systems that, despite their complexity, reflect the pronunciation quite accurately. Although a single sound may vary in spelling across words, consistent orthographic rules and diacritical marks ensure generally predictable pronunciation with few exceptions. As a result, dictionaries for these languages rarely require phonetic notation. English is an exception. Its spelling generally does not allow prediction of pronunciation. This poses minimal issues for native speakers, who acquire pronunciation through daily exposure, but presents significant difficulties for non-native learners.

In languages like Arabic or Hebrew, which use abjads (consonantal alphabets), spelling does not reflect vowel pronunciation. Although diacritics are not used in everyday writing, these languages

employ complex marking systems in educational and other formal contexts to indicate vowels without altering standard orthography. Similarly, in pedagogical materials for foreign learners of Russian, word stress and the letter *ě* are typically marked to facilitate correct pronunciation.

The idea of supporting English pronunciation through modified orthographic or diacritic-based systems is not new. However, earlier proposals typically required changes to conventional spelling, which may explain their limited adoption. The present proposal therefore explores an alternative strategy: supplementing standard spelling with diacritical marking. Given English's role as the world's primary lingua franca, it is worth examining whether such an approach can support relatively predictable pronunciation for international users. This article argues that, contrary to appearances, the answer is affirmative if the goal is not bidirectional transparency, but reliable pronunciation decoding from text, as found in languages such as French or Polish. However, due to the lack of a unified standard pronunciation in English and interdialectal differences, it is not possible to create a notation that would be both universal and accurate.

In 2025, a preliminary proof-of-concept study on a related diacritical notation was published (Stachowicz 2025), demonstrating the feasibility of a diacritical system for English capable of conveying pronunciation without altering standard spelling. The present article introduces a revised and significantly simplified notation system that is not backward-compatible with the earlier concept.

As a non-native user, the author decided to create the notation to make English pronunciation more accessible for learners and users like himself. The writing system, through the introduction of diacritical marks and certain rules for their interpretation, is intended to allow pronunciation to be inferred in a way similar to that of other languages. The method is primarily useful for non-native English users, who may struggle with pronunciation, not for native speakers, whose difficulties may lie in spelling.

The following principles were adopted:

- Diacritical marks have to be placed directly on the standard spelling; the core principle is that standard orthography must remain unchanged once the diacritical marks are removed.
- The diacritical marks should be quite intuitive for users familiar with diacritical marks used in other European languages and should not primarily suggest incorrect pronunciation.
- The diacritic notation need not be fully unambiguous and may be context-dependent, as long as any ambiguities can be resolved using simple, consistent rules aligned with general English conventions.
- The set of characters (letters with diacritics) should cover standard English phonemes and indicate pronunciation as unambiguously as possible. Simplifications and ambiguities are allowed if the contrasts necessary for intelligibility are maintained (particularly in accordance with the Lingua Franca Core principles).
- Exceptions are allowed on a limited scale, i.e. to the extent that can be remembered, and in the case of proper names and words with borrowed spelling.

This article presents a method for indicating the pronunciation of English words meeting the conditions specified above. Surprisingly, from the perspective of the author's initial expectations, this proves both feasible and relatively straightforward. Much English spelling appears chaotic, suggesting that only a comprehensive spelling reform could resolve the issues. However, a closer examination reveals that much of this "mess" is merely apparent; most patterns reflect historical pronunciation, and actual irregularities—primarily resulting from orthographic borrowing from foreign languages—are relatively few. The system utilizes these regularities to support clear and intelligible ELF pronunciation.

The diacritic-based system is named ELF Diacritic Notation (ELF DN), reflecting its primary design to meet ELF intelligibility requirements. It is intended to provide a default, intelligibility-based

pronunciation framework within the limits of the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). It may not capture all subtle phonetic distinctions of native varieties, but it is designed to avoid suggesting pronunciations outside LFC. Skilled users can exceed its guidance, while less proficient users following the basic ELF DN pattern are likely to be understood.

Additionally, the system is scalable: it is possible to introduce additional diacritic marks to allow for a more precise representation of pronunciation in British or American English, reaching a level of accuracy comparable to IPA notation.

The notation can be used in international communication among non-native speakers, helping them achieve intelligible reading and supporting the learning of English as a foreign language, particularly for older students, independent learners, or those who rely primarily on visual memory. It is especially suitable for self-study tutorials.

1.2. Explanations of Terms, Simplifications, and Abbreviations Used

This article employs widely known and commonly used terms. For practical reasons, however, many simplifications and abbreviations have been applied, whose meanings may occasionally differ from their precise scientific definitions or depend on context. The following explanations are provided for clarification:

- Sound – a basic unit of pronunciation that can be a consonant or a vowel; vowels usually form the core of a syllable, with consonants surrounding them.
- Phoneme – the smallest unit of sound in a language that can change the meaning of a word. In this article, it usually refers to the standard dictionary phonemes used for transcribing English pronunciation. The phonetic realisation of a phoneme may vary slightly depending on the context.
- Phonemic transcription – a transcription using IPA symbols to represent phonemes, conventionally enclosed in slashes / /, without indicating phonetic variations or allophones (e.g., dark /l/, flapped /t/).
- Phonetic transcription – a transcription using IPA symbols, enclosed with brackets [], reflecting allophones and phonetic variations of standard phonemes.
- Diacritic (mark, symbol) – modifying mark added to a letter (e.g., acute ´, macron ¯)
- Character – a letter combined with a diacritic (e.g., ⟨à, é, ï, ö⟩).
- Grapheme – a letter, character, or their sequence corresponding to a phoneme; two-letter graphemes are digraphs, three-letter graphemes are trigraphs.
- Digraph – a sequence of two letters that represents a phoneme; there are consonant digraphs (⟨sh, th, ph⟩ etc.) and vowel digraphs (e.g., ⟨ai, oo, oa⟩, also ⟨ew, ay⟩).
- Consonants – depending on context, this term may refer to sounds and phonemes, or to letters or digraphs representing consonants. They are represented as ⟨C⟩ in spelling, /C/ in phonemic transcription, and [C] in phonetic transcription.
- Vowels – phonemes or sounds that are monophthongs, diphthongs, or triphthongs. Can also refer to letters or digraphs representing vowels. Represented as ⟨V⟩ in spelling, /V/ in phonemic transcription, and [V] in phonetic transcription.
- Hiatus – sequence of two vowels belonging to separate syllables.
- Diphthongs – in this article, the term most often refers to standard English diphthong phonemes /eɪ, aɪ, aʊ, oɪ, əʊ|oʊ/, including glide–vowel sequences such as /ju:/, and, more broadly, [jʊ, jə], as well as centring diphthongs and triphthongs /eə, ɪə, ʊə, jʊə/.

- Long monophthongs – in this article, the term mainly refers to typically long-pronounced monophthongs represented by phonemes /ɑ:, i:, ɔ:, u:/, regardless of their actual phonetic length.
- Full short vowels (or short vowels) – the phonemes /æ, e, ɒ, ʌ, ʊ, ɪ/. For practical purposes, the category is extended in this article to include the ‘nurse’ vowel /ɜ: ~ ə/ and the American ‘lot’ vowel /ɑ/.
- Weak vowels – /ʊ, ɪ, i/ in unstressed syllables.
- Reduced vowel – schwa /ə/.
- Stressed syllable (str. syl.) – syllable carrying either primary or secondary stress.
- Stressed vowel (str. vw.) – vowel occurring in a primary or secondary stressed syllable.
- Unstressed syllable or vowel (unstr. syl./vw.) – syllable or vowel without primary or secondary stress.
- Closed and open syllables – terms used here in the orthographic sense: an open syllable ends with a vowel letter, while a closed syllable ends with a consonant. Closed syllables within words are often signalled by a consonant cluster or double consonant (e.g., *basket, socket, classic, system*). Syllables ending in a silent -e (e.g., -ate, -ure) are classified as orthographically open.
- R-closed syllable (R-cl. syl.) – term refers to a stressed syllable closed by the letter ⟨r⟩ (i.e., where ⟨r⟩ is followed by a consonant or the end of the word); endings such as -ore or -ure are not considered R-closed.
- Palatalisation – consonant change in which sounds like /t, d, s, z/ turn into affricates or postalveolar consonants (e.g., /tʃ, dʒ, ʃ, ʒ/); often associated with yod coalescence, i.e., loss of /j/ following a consonant.

1.3. Dialects and Standards of English Pronunciation

English, a global language, has diverse pronunciation variants across different countries. The two primary reference dialects for teaching are British English (BrE) and American English (AmE). Non-native students are typically taught one of two standard pronunciation variants: British Received Pronunciation (RP) or General American (GA).

International English (IntE) is a broadly standard-based variety of English used internationally, oriented toward native-speaker norms but tolerant of variation. IntE aims to preserve native-like stress patterns, while allowing limited phonemic variation, reflecting established dialectal norms. Tolerance of pronunciation differences in IntE:

- Vowels in unstressed syllables: variation in vowel quality is widely tolerated, including differences between /ə/, weak /ɪ/, and /jə/, as long as the syllable remains unstressed.
- Vowels in stressed syllables: vowel variation is tolerated only when it corresponds to natural differences between major native dialects (e.g. RP vs. GA).

Commonly tolerated vowel correspondences include: /ɒ ~ ɑ/ (LOT vowel), /əʊ ~ oʊ/ (GOAT vowel).

Vowel differences generally not tolerated in stressed syllables include:

/ɑ ~ ʌ/, /ɔ: ~ ɒ/, /ju: ~ jʊ/, /u: ~ ʊ/, /i ~ ɪ/.

- Other forms of dialectal variation that are generally tolerated include:
 - rhotic vs. non-rhotic pronunciation
 - r-colouring vs. vowel + /r/ sequences
 - presence vs. absence of vowel breaking or centring before /r/

English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) is used as a contact language among non-native speakers and prioritises intelligibility over adherence to native-speaker norms. The pronunciation features that are crucial for maintaining intelligibility are defined within the **Lingua Franca Core (LFC)**.

In particular, the following pronunciation features should be preserved in ELF communication:

- Consonant contrasts, with a few exceptions (for example /θ, ð/ → /f, v/) which are tolerated.
- Final /r/ should be pronounced (as in American English), rather than dropped as in British English.
- The contrast between so-called long and short vowels.
- Full vowels in stressed syllables: stressed vowels should not be reduced.
- Vowels should be shortened before voiceless consonants and lengthened before voiced consonants (sat, sad [sæt-sæ:d], pick, pig [pɪk-pɪ:g]).

At the same time, ELF tolerates pronunciation variation to a broader extent:

- Syllable-level stress variation is generally tolerated, provided that lexical stress contrasts are preserved and full vowels from originally stressed syllables are not reduced, even if the stress is shifted.
- Vowels in unstressed syllables: variation in vowel quality is widely tolerated, including the use of full vowels instead of reduced vowels, as long as no additional lexical stress is introduced. The following vowel variation groups are commonly tolerated in unstressed syllables: [ju: ~ jʊ ~ jə], [u ~ ʊ ~ ə], [i ~ ɪ], [ɪ ~ ə], [jʊ ~ jə ~ ə].
- Vowels in stressed syllables: variation in vowel quality is tolerated only to a limited extent, as long as intelligibility is not impaired. Under this condition, the following variations are commonly tolerated in stressed syllables: [ɒ ~ ɑ ~ ʌ], [ɔ: ~ ɒ].

1.4. IPA transcription systems for representing pronunciation in English dictionaries

In English dictionaries, pronunciation is most commonly represented by simplified IPA phonemic transcription. Unlike phonetic transcription (written in square brackets []), phonemic transcription (written in slashes //) omits allophonic variation, i.e., context-dependent realizations of a phoneme that do not change word meaning.

Different dictionaries adopt slightly varying conventions for IPA phonemic transcription. For example, some use /e/ while others use /ɛ/ for the same phoneme. Similarly, some use /i/, others /ɪ/, or both (e.g., /ɪ/ and /i/) to reflect pronunciation differences or lexical distinctions.

British RP and American GA use largely comparable IPA phoneme inventories, differing mainly in their vowel systems (see Table 1). One of the most significant differences is that RP is a non-rhotic dialect, whereas GA is rhotic. In GA, word-final /r/ is always pronounced, whereas in RP it is pronounced only before a vowel or in linking /r/ contexts (e.g., car vs. car and).

Table 1.

The phoneme sets in RP and GA

Consonants	RP, GA	/b/, /d/, /dʒ/, /f/, /g/, /h/, /j/, /l/, /m/, /n/, /ŋ/, /p/, /k/, /r/, /s/, /ʃ/, /tʃ/, /t/, /θ/, /ð/, /v/, /w/, /z/, /ʒ/
Vowels	RP	/æ/, /ɑ:/, /ʌ/, /e/, /ə/, /ɜ:/, /ɪ/, /i:/, /ɒ/, /ɔ:/, /ʊ/, /u:/
	GA	/æ/, /ɑ:/, /ʌ/, /e/, /ə/, /ɚ/, /ɜ:/, /ɪ/, /i:/, /ɔ:/, /ʊ/, /u:/
Diphthongs	RP	/eɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɔɪ/, /əʊ/, /aʊ/, /ju:/
	GA	/eɪ/, /aɪ/, /ɔɪ/, /oʊ/, /aʊ/, /ju/

In addition to the standard phonemes shown in Table 1, dictionaries also use the so-called neutralised phonemes /i/ and /u/, which refer to vowels in unstressed syllables where the contrast between /i: ~ ɪ/ and /u: ~ ʊ/ is neutralised.

In most cases, the phonemes used in RP and GA are either identical or have direct equivalents, such as /ɒ – ɑ/, /ɜ: – ə/, or /əʊ – oʊ/. For corresponding RP/GA phonemes (dialectal equivalents), the following notation is used in this article: /ɒ|ɑ/, /əʊ|oʊ/ (or /oʊ/), /ɜ:|ə/ (or /ɜ:/).

This article focuses on the application of a diacritic system to International English, particularly within the framework of ELF. While both British and American English are taken into account, GA appears to provide a more functionally suitable reference model in certain respects (e.g., rhoticity), in accordance with LFC principles.

The Cambridge Dictionary is used as the reference source for phonemic transcription in this article, as it provides parallel RP and GA transcriptions and employs a consistent and widely recognised convention.

2. Analysis of the relationship between standard English spelling and pronunciation and its implications for the proposed diacritic system

The design of the diacritic system was based on an analysis of the existing relationships between spelling and pronunciation. Such an analysis was necessary in order to satisfy the fundamental assumption that the standard spelling should remain unchanged, while the system should at the same time remain relatively transparent and practical in use.

It was assumed that the diacritic notation should mark the pronunciation of sounds only to the extent necessary for intelligibility, while omitting features that follow from the general principles and rules linking spelling and pronunciation.

The present article does not discuss the analyses in detail. Instead, it presents only those conclusions that are relevant to the proposed diacritic system.

2.1. Conclusions from the analysis of consonant spelling and pronunciation

The correct pronunciation of consonants plays a crucial role in communication. In most cases, consonant letters indicate their pronunciation relatively clearly; however, in many instances the relationship between spelling and pronunciation is less straightforward.

For consonants, relatively stable rules linking spelling and pronunciation can be identified. This makes it possible to limit the use of diacritics to cases where such rules do not apply. In the context of ELF, the application of these rules and familiarity with the main exceptions makes it possible to avoid unintelligibility in the vast majority of cases.

For the purposes of ELF, it may therefore be sufficient to introduce diacritics only to mark communicatively significant deviations from the standard pronunciation in cases where the number of exceptions is considerable, namely:

- ⟨ch⟩ pronounced /ʃ/ – proposed notation: ⟨ĉh⟩
- ⟨ch⟩ pronounced /k/ – proposed notation: ⟨ċh⟩
- ⟨g⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ pronounced /g/ – proposed notation: ⟨ḡ⟩

In addition, the following cases occur frequently:

- Palatalisation /t, d, s, z/ → /tʃ, dʒ, ʃ, ʒ/. In most cases this can be described by rules, and occasional mispronunciation rarely results in unintelligibility. However, there are words in which palatalisation is standard across all dialects and cannot be explained by general rules.

- Silent consonant letters. These generally do not encode phonological information relevant for distinguishing meaning and typically occur in contexts that can be described by rules or lists of exceptions.
- Voicing of typically voiceless consonants: ⟨s⟩ → /z, ʒ/, ⟨th⟩ → /ð/, ⟨x⟩ → /gz/. This usually occurs between vowels and can be intuitively predicted from context (see Table 8); the risk of misunderstanding in the case of occasional mispronunciation is minimal.

Marking these deviations in ELF is therefore generally unnecessary, although it may be useful for language learners. Optionally, ELF notation may mark palatalisation in certain irregular cases.

2.2. Conclusions from the analysis of vowel spelling and pronunciation

The pronunciation of vowels depends on context, for example on whether they occur in stressed or unstressed syllables, in closed or open syllables, or before the letter ⟨r⟩. General phonological rules can be used to infer their correct pronunciation; however, these rules operate inconsistently and are difficult for an average user to apply.

Stressed syllables

According to the Lingua Franca Core, maintaining vowel contrasts in stressed syllables is crucial for intelligibility in ELF. In stressed syllables (primary or secondary), the vowel letters ⟨a⟩, ⟨e⟩, ⟨o⟩, ⟨u⟩, ⟨i⟩, and ⟨y⟩ are usually pronounced as:

- short full vowels /æ/, /e/, /ɒ/, /ʊ/, /ʌ/, /ɪ/
- long monophthongs /ɑː/, /iː/, /ɔː/, /uː/
- diphthongs /eɪ/, /aɪ/, /əʊ|oʊ/, /juː/

In addition, vowel pronunciation is modified under the influence of a following consonant /r/. These cases are not discussed here, as they are addressed in the next section (2.3).

The approximate frequency of phonemic realisations of vowel letters in stressed syllables (excluding the influence of the consonant /r/) is presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Frequency of phonemic realisations of vowel letters in stressed syllables

	Often	Sometimes	In exceptions
a	/æ, ɑː, eɪ/	/ɔː, ɒ(BrE)/	/e/
e	/e, iː/	/eɪ/	/ɪ/
i, y	/ɪ, iː, aɪ/		
o	/ɒ ɑ, ɔː, əʊ oʊ/	/uː, ʌ/	/ʊ, ɪ/
u	/ʌ, uː, juː/		/ʊ, ɪ, e/

The table shows (column “Often”) that, for vowel letters in stressed syllables, the three primary phonemic realisations typically correspond to one specific vowel each: a short full vowel, a long monophthong, and a diphthong. Other realisations occur infrequently or are exceptional. This pattern reflects a largely stable system underlying the pronunciation of stressed vowels, providing a useful guide for the design of the proposed diacritic system.

It is also worth noting that in English diacritics are used to indicate the pronunciation of é → /eɪ/ (e.g., café, étude).

Based on these observations, the primary diacritic distinctions for stressed vowels in ELF should be:

- marking diphthong pronunciation – proposed notation: ⟨á, é, í, ý, ó, ú⟩ (consistent to é → /eɪ/)

- marking long monophthong pronunciation – proposed notation: ⟨ā, ē, ī, ō, ū⟩
- marking short stressed vowels – proposed notation: ⟨à, è, ì, ÿ, ò, ù⟩
- highlighting frequent and communicatively significant deviations from standard pronunciation, in particular ⟨o⟩ → /u:/ – proposed notation: ⟨ö⟩ (mark shape resembling the letter U).

Cases such as ⟨a⟩ → /ɔ:, ɒ/ (often after /w/ and before dark /l/) can generally be replaced with /ɑ:/ in ELF without risking unintelligibility, and can therefore all be marked identically without introducing an additional diacritic.

Marking differences such as a → /ɔ: ~ ɒ/, a → /ɑ: ~ ɒ/, or o → /ɒ|ɑ: ~ ʌ/ (less communicatively significant and generally tolerated in ELF) may nevertheless be useful for learners aiming at correct pronunciation in AmE or BrE.

Other exceptions are very rare and can be memorised; they do not require diacritic marking.

Unstressed vowels

In unstressed syllables (neither primary nor secondary), vowels typically undergo reduction and are usually pronounced as a schwa /ə/, or sometimes as weak /ɪ/ or /i/, or as /jə/ and /jɪ/.

Significant interdialectal variation in the pronunciation of unstressed vowels is common, and variation in vowel quality is widely tolerated in ELF, including the use of full vowels instead of reduced vowels, provided that no additional lexical stress is introduced. In particular, the following vowel variation groups are commonly tolerated in unstressed syllables:

- [ju: ~ jʊ ~ jə]
- [u ~ ʊ ~ ə]
- [i ~ ɪ]
- [ɪ ~ ə]
- [jʊ ~ jə ~ ə]

Vowels in unstressed syllables do not generally encode communicatively relevant information, and mispronunciation of these vowels is unlikely to cause misunderstanding in ELF. Based on this, marking unstressed vowels with diacritics in ELF is generally unnecessary.

2.3. Influence of the consonant /r/ on the pronunciation of preceding vowels

In English, the consonant /r/ (or the letter ⟨r⟩) affects the pronunciation of preceding vowels in stressed syllables. The exact realisation depends on whether the syllable is open (when a vowel follows the ⟨r⟩) or an R-closed syllable (when ⟨r⟩ precedes a consonant or ends a word). In non-rhotic British English, /r/ is silent before a consonant and at the end of a word.

The influence of /r/ on vowel pronunciation varies between dialects, but it is generally very regular. Based on the analysis of spelling and pronunciation, the following conclusions are relevant for the design of the diacritic system:

R-closed stressed syllables:

In sequences such as ⟨er, ir, yr, wor, ur, ear, our, -eur⟩, the vowel is pronounced as /ɜ:|ɜ:/ (the nurse vowel). The short full vowels /e, ɪ, ɒ|ɑ, ʌ, ʊ/ do not occur in this context. Vowels /ɜ:|ɜ:/ (except for rare exceptions, e.g., *colonel*) do not appear elsewhere. This regularity allows the use of a single diacritic strategy, marking only the stress: ⟨èr, ìr, ÿr, òr, ùr, èar, òur, -èur⟩, without introducing a separate diacritic for /ɜ:|ɜ:/.

R-following stressed syllables (centring diphthongs and dialectal variation):

Vowels /eɪ, i:, u:, ju:, aɪ, aʊ/ before /r/ in BrE are transformed into centring diphthongs. In AmE, the so-called “breaking before /r/” does not occur; instead, long vowels /eɪ, i:, u:, ju:/ are realised as short vowels /e, ɪ, ʊ, jʊ/.

This regularity allows the application of a universal diacritic notation: ⟨ár, ír, ūr, úr, ír⟩. These can be interpreted in BrE as /eɪə(r), ɪə(r), ʊə(r), jʊə(r), aɪə(r)/, and in AmE as /er, ɪr, ʊr, jʊr, aɪr/, without the need for additional diacritics.

2.4. Vowel digraphs and hiatus

The term “vowel digraph” refers to a sequence of two letters representing a single vowel phoneme. Some digraphs involve a semi-vowel letter, e.g., ⟨aw, ew, ow, oy⟩. There is also a three-letter sequence ⟨eau⟩, known as a trigraph.

Sequences representing vowels in separate syllables (so-called hiatuses) are not considered digraphs.

Vowel digraphs can be pronounced as either monophthongs or diphthongs. They typically form the nucleus of stressed syllables, while unstressed digraphs usually appear in endings, for example: ⟨-ain, -ean, -eant, -eur, -our, -ous, -ier, -ue⟩.

Although dominant pronunciation variants of digraphs can be identified, clear rules for predicting their pronunciation do not exist. Their pronunciation may therefore be indicated with diacritics. For this purpose, clear notation conventions are required that avoid ambiguity while remaining easy to read. These conventions can be established relatively transparently without introducing additional diacritics.

Hiatus may sometimes cause ambiguity if the reader does not recognise the syllable boundary and interprets a sequence of vowels as a digraph representing a single phoneme. This may also occur in sequences ⟨CiV⟩, where /i/ is often lost and the preceding consonants ⟨c, s, t⟩ become palatalised, which normally does not happen in hiatus. Marking hiatus may therefore help indicate separate vowel pronunciation and distinguish such cases. The dieresis—used in some languages to mark the separate pronunciation of adjacent vowels (e.g. *Citroën*)—is proposed as an optional supplementary mark.

3. Description of the proposed ELF Diacritic Notation

The main assumptions of the proposed ELF Diacritic Notation were outlined in Section 1.1. The system presented here meets the requirements described there: it limits the use of diacritical marks and avoids applying them where they are not necessary for correctly interpreting pronunciation by a learner who has mastered the basic patterns and rules of English spelling and pronunciation.

The system allows for reduced phonetic precision while maintaining intelligibility of word meanings and tolerating exceptions. Diacritics are applied only where patterns and rules are insufficiently stable or where exceptions are too numerous to be memorized reliably.

3.1. Proposed set of diacritics

Based on the analysis of the relationships between pronunciation and spelling, the following set of diacritics and characters for the ELF Diacritic Notation has been proposed.

For consonants:

- acute accent (´) for ⟨čh⟩ pronounced /j/
- macron (¯) for ⟨čh⟩ pronounced /k/ and for ⟨ġ⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ pronounced /g/

The characters ⟨ć, ś, ť, đ⟩ are optional and may be used to indicate exceptions, which are fairly numerous and difficult to memorise.

For vowels, diacritics are introduced to mark their realisation as diphthongs, long monophthongs, or stressed short vowels.

- acute accent (´) marks diphthongs
- macron (¯) marks long monophthongs
- breve (˘) marks ⟨ð⟩ → /u:/
- grave accent (`) marks stressed short vowels, indicating stress regardless of their exact phonemic value

Short vowels in unstressed syllables remain unmarked. Vowels in unstressed syllables are marked when pronounced as diphthongs or long monophthongs. Unmarked vowels in unstressed syllables are usually pronounced as reduced or weak. Full short vowels are rare in unstressed syllables.

As a supplementary mark, the dieresis may be used to indicate hiatus.

The set of diacritics and characters for the ELF Diacritic Notation is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3.

Diacritical marks proposed for ELF notation with a description of their function and meaning

Description of the Marks	Meaning	Characters Used in Notation
Marks for consonant letters		
Macron (¯)	Hard /k, g/	⟨ch⟩→/k/; ⟨ḡ⟩→/g/
Acute accent (´)	“Hushing” /ʃ/	⟨ch⟩ →/ʃ/; (⟨ć, ś⟩ →/ʃ/ optional)
Caron (optional)	Africates	⟨ḍ⟩ →/dʒ/; ⟨ṭ⟩ →/tʃ/
Marks for letters-vowels		
Acute accent (´)	Diphthongs /eɪ, aɪ, əʊ, ju:/	⟨á, é⟩→/eɪ/; ⟨í, ý⟩→/aɪ/; ⟨ó⟩→/əʊ oʊ/; ⟨ú⟩→/ju:/
Macron (¯)	Long monophthongs /ɑ:, i:, ɔ:, u:/	⟨ā⟩→/ɑ:/; ⟨ē, ī, ŷ⟩→/i:/; ⟨ō⟩→/ɔ:/; ⟨ū⟩→/u:/
Breve (˘ - resembling U)	Long /u:/	⟨ö̆⟩ →/u:/
Grave accent (`)	Stressed full short vowels /æ, e, ɒ ɑ, ʌ, ʊ, ɪ/ or /ɜ: ɜ/	⟨à, è, ò, ù, ì, ÿ⟩
Dieresis (optional)	Unstressed vowel in hiatus: reduced or weak vowel, or hiatic /i/	⟨ä, ë, ö, ü, ï, ÿ⟩

3.2. Rules of Marking – Editor’s Guide

This section describes the rules and conventions for marking letters with diacritical signs. In ELF Diacritic Notation, the aim is to maintain a notation that is dialect-neutral. However, dialectal variation may occasionally lead to different diacritic markings.

In exceptional cases where the rules described below do not allow a satisfactory representation in any major dialect, markings should approximate an intelligible pronunciation as closely as possible.

3.2.1. Function Words

As a rule, diacritical marks should not be used in frequently occurring function words such as:

- articles, prepositions, pronouns, conjunctions, and particles
- auxiliary and modal verbs such as be, have, do, can, may, shall, and will and all their forms (are, would, etc.)
- simple numbers

High-frequency function words often have atypical pronunciations and are learned as whole words; diacritics are unnecessary.

3.2.2. Consonant Marking

Diacritical marks should be used only for irregular pronunciations:

- ⟨g̃⟩ before ⟨e, i, y⟩ → /g/
- ⟨ĉh⟩ → /k/
- ⟨čh⟩ → /ʃ/

Optional marks ⟨ć, ś, ț, đ⟩ indicate palatalised realisations:

- ⟨ć, ś⟩ → /ʃ/,
- ⟨đ⟩ → /dʒ/,
- ⟨ț⟩ → /tʃ/

Optional marks ⟨ć, ś, ț, đ⟩ may be used for exceptions showing palatalisation in both AmE and BrE (e.g., *ócean, śugar, insũre, èdũcate, àctũal*). They should not be used:

- where palatalisation is not standard in both dialects (e.g. *sensual, dúal, dúring*) or
- where palatalisation follows regular rules, e.g.:
 - sequences ciV (endings *-cial, -cian, -cious, -cient*)
 - endings *-sion, -sia(n)*
 - endings *-dure, -ture, -stion*

Detailed rules, examples, and exceptions are provided in Table 8 in Section 4.

3.2.3. Diphthong and Long Monophthong Marking

Acute accent (´) marks diphthongs:

- ⟨á, é⟩ → /eɪ/
- ⟨í, ý⟩ → /aɪ/
- ⟨ó⟩ → /əʊ|oʊ/
- ⟨ú⟩ → /ju:/

Macron (¯) marks long monophthongs:

- ⟨ā⟩ → /ɑ:/ (also /ɔ:/ or /ɒ/)
- ⟨ē, ī, ȳ⟩ → /i:/
- ⟨ō⟩ → /ɔ:/
- ⟨ū⟩ → /u:/

⟨ā⟩ is also used for ⟨a⟩ pronounced /ɔ:/ or /ɒ/ in BrE, unifying cross-dialectal variation.

Words like *dual, dune, tune, tutor, Tuesday* may vary in ⟨u⟩ pronunciation (/ju:/, /u:/, /dʒu:/, /tʃu:/). Preferred marking is ⟨ú⟩; ⟨ū⟩ is also acceptable.

Breve (˘) in ⟨ö⟩ marks its irregular pronunciation /u:/.

Detailed rules, examples, and exceptions are given in Table 6.

3.2.4. Stress Marking for Short Vowels

The grave accent (̀) in ELF notation is used to indicate primary or secondary stressed short vowels, including ‘nurse vowels’ /ɜ:|ɜ/. Short stressed vowels should be marked in the same way regardless of their precise phonemic value.

Unstressed vowels should not be marked, even if they are pronounced as full vowels and do not undergo reduction (e.g. *amphibia*). Such cases are rare. An exception may be proper names, where a clear indication of pronunciation may be important (e.g. *Zàmbēzi*).

Short one-syllable words are typically stressed, so stress-marking grave accents are unnecessary (e.g. *cat*, *jump*). They should be omitted unless vowel digraphs occur, in which case marking is applied to avoid ambiguity (e.g. *hèad*, *frìend*, *còugh*).

Most two-syllable words are stressed on the first syllable. In these cases, grave accents may be omitted for first-syllable vowels, provided the word does not contain a vowel digraph, diphthong, or long monophthong, whose presence could introduce ambiguity or suggest stress on the final syllable. Examples: *syrup*, *limit*, *happy*, but *mèadow*, *coùrage*, *còffee*, *bìrdsēed*, *pàtìó*.

In all other cases, grave accents should follow the general rules.

3.2.5. Vowel Digraph Marking

English vowel digraphs may represent monophthongs or diphthongs, and their pronunciation is highly irregular. In ELF Diacritic Notation, diacritic marking indicates the phonemic value of a digraph as unambiguously as possible, allowing only a few exceptional cases. Certain conventional rules are applied for this purpose.

Regular marking rules:

- As a general principle, diacritic should be applied to the letter that determines the phonemic value of the digraph, following the same rules as for single-letter graphemes.
- If a digraph's phonemic value could be indicated by either letter, the first letter is marked by default.
- Unstressed digraphs corresponding to schwa or weak /ɪ/ remain unmarked.

Using the above rules, most digraph-phoneme correspondences can be unambiguously marked.

However, the following require special treatment:

- ⟨ee⟩ → /ɪ/, ⟨-ee⟩ → /i/ (unmarked, note that ⟨ēe⟩ → /i:/)
- ⟨òo⟩ → /ʌ/, ⟨oo⟩ → /ʊ/ (unmarked, note that ⟨ǒo⟩ → /u:/, ⟨ōo⟩ → /ɔ:/)
- ⟨oi, oy⟩ → /ɔɪ/ (unmarked, diphthong)
- ⟨ew⟩ → /ju:, u:, əʊ|oʊ/ (unmarked, context-dependent pronunciation)
- ⟨-eau, au⟩ → /əʊ|oʊ/ (unmarked, rare)
- ⟨òū, òw, āū⟩ → /aʊ/ (diphthong)
- ⟨àì, ày⟩ → /e/ (rare)
- ⟨āu, āw⟩ → /ɔ: ~ ɒ ~ ɑ:/ (common marking for dialect-dependent pronunciation)

In exceptional cases not covered by the above rules, digraphs remain unmarked or may be marked with a grave accent to indicate word stress (e.g., *does*, *Freud*, *lièutenant*, *massèuse*).

Hiatuses (sequences of vowels in separate syllables) are marked by applying the rules for single vowels to each letter. Overlap between digraph and hiatus marking may occur, e.g., *reàlity*, *reāct*, *créate*, *mèdiēval*, *clíent*, *rūin*, *fúel*. To avoid ambiguity, the dieresis may be optionally applied (see Section 3.2.7).

Detailed conventions for marking all vowel graphemes and their sequences with ⟨r⟩ are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4.

Diacritical marking of vowel graphemes and their sequences with ⟨r⟩.

Phoneme (BrE AmE)	ELF Diacritic Notation of the Phonemes		Remarks
	Simple Vowel Graphemes	Vowel Digraphs Blue: irregular marking	
<u>Diphthongs</u>			
/eɪ/	á, é	áu, ái, áy, éa, éi, éy	
/aɪ/	í, ý	eý, íe, ýe,	
/ɔɪ/		oí, oy	
/əʊ oʊ/		óa, óo, óu, ów, (-eau, ew, au)	
/aʊ/		òū, òw, (āū)	
/ju:/	ú	eú, úe, úi, ew, eaú	
<u>Long and Short Stressed Monophthongs</u>			
/ɑ:/	ā	eā	
/ɒ ɑ:, ɔ:/	ā	āu, āw,	Unified ELF cross-dialect marking
/ɔ:/	ō	ōa, ōo	
/i:/	ē, ī	ēa, īe, ēi, ēy, ēe,	
/u:/	ō, ū	ōo, oū, ūe, ūi, eū, ew	
/æ/	à	(àì)	
/e/	è, (à)	èa, iè, èi, (ài, ày)	
/ɪ/(strong)	ì	ee, eì, ìe, uì,	
/ɒ ɑ:/	ò	òu	
/ʌ/	ò, ù	où, òo	
/ʊ/	(ù)	oo	
<u>Unstressed Vowels</u>			
/ə/	a, e, i, o, u,	ai, ea, eu, ou, eau	
weak /ɪ/	a, e, i	ui	
happy /i/	-i, -y	-ee, -ey, -ie, -ied, -ies	
/jə, jʊ, ju/	u		
other short unstressed	left unmarked		
unstressed long or diphthong	marked according to the general rules		
<u>Vowel Sequences with R</u>			
/ɜ: ɝ:/	èr, ìr, òr, ùr, ÿr	òur, èur, èar	
/ɪə(r) ɪr/	ēr, -ēre	ēar, ēer, (ēir), ìer	marked like /i:r/
/ʊə(r) ʊr/	ūr, -ūre	oūr	marked like /u:r/
/eə(r) er/	ár, -áre	áir, éar, (éir)	marked like /eɪr/
/aɪə(r) aɪr/	-íre, -ýre		marked like /aɪr/
/aʊə(r) aʊr/		òūr	marked like /aʊr/
/jʊə(r) jʊr/	úr, -úre	eúr	marked like /ju:r/

Parentheses indicate rare or exceptional cases

3.2.6. Marking of Vowel-R Sequences

Vowels and diphthongs in sequences with ⟨r⟩ should be marked according to the general rules for vowels, with the following specifications:

- Vr sequences in R-closed stressed syllables pronounced as /ɜ:|ɝ/ should be marked with a grave accent: (èr, ìr, òr, ùr, ÿr, òur, èur, èar).
- A unified marking convention for BrE, AmE, and ELF is adopted for sequences that correspond to breaking before /r/ in BrE. Diacritics should be applied so that the vowel represents the intended phoneme as indicated below:

- /eə(r)|er/ → like /eɪr/ i.e. ⟨ár, -áre, áir, éar, éir⟩
- /ɪə(r)|ɪr/ → like /i:r/ i.e. ⟨ēr, -ēre, ēar, ēer, ēir, ier⟩
- /aɪə(r)|aɪr/ → like /aɪr/ i.e. ⟨-íre, -ýre, ír, ýr⟩
- /aʊə(r)|aʊr/ → like /aʊr/ i.e. ⟨ðūr⟩
- /ʊə(r)|ʊr/ → like /u:r/ i.e. ⟨-ūre, oūr⟩
- /jʊə(r)|jʊr/ → like /ju:r/ i.e. ⟨úr, -úre, eúr⟩

In particular, the sequences /er, ɪr, ʊr/ should not be marked as ⟨èr, ìr, ùr⟩ to avoid misinterpretation as /ɜ:|ɝ/.

Detailed conventions for marking vowel sequences with ⟨r⟩ are provided in Table 4.

3.2.7. Hiatus Marking (optional)

Some vowel sequences represent hiatus rather than digraphs and may require marking to avoid misinterpretation. The dieresis (¨) may be used to indicate separate pronunciation of adjacent vowels.

To avoid conflicts with other diacritics, the dieresis should be placed above the unmarked vowel (not over a stressed, long or diphthong). Examples:

- *fúëi, crúëi, súët, rüin, sólóíst, prótozöä, crëäte*

In sequences ⟨CiV⟩, the dieresis marks hiatic /i/:

- *bàstion, celèstia, pàtió, tiāra, ètìòlogy, cēsium, càlcium, Cèlsius*

The dieresis is not required when both vowels already carry diacritics, as this normally indicates a hiatus:

- *dúèt, cóàguláte, óásis, zòòlogy, cóòperate, ìntúition, cóìncidence*

Dieresis should not be applied in common prefixes, e.g., *reènter, deóodorant*.

3.3. Reading ELF Diacritic Notation – User’s Guide

Although the ELF diacritic notation system has been fully described in the previous chapter, additional guidance is needed for effective use. Since the notation does not fully specify pronunciation, reading texts correctly requires not only recognizing diacritical marks and characters but also applying typical spelling-to-sound patterns.

Learning these patterns is not required by rote, as they are generally acquired naturally during English study. Nevertheless, understanding them can help users read both diacritic texts and standard English more accurately.

The following subsections summarize the key rules that a non-native reader should follow when using ELF Diacritic Notation.

3.3.1. Reading Vowels

In ELF Diacritic Notation, vowels that are long, diphthongs, or stressed short vowels are marked, as these are critical for intelligibility. Clear articulation of marked and stressed vowels is crucial and generally sufficient.

Table 5 shows how vowels are pronounced according to ELF DN marking. The default ELF pronunciation shown is a generally intelligible form to use when the exact pronunciation is unknown to the user. Crucial exceptions are rare and can be memorised - the most important cases are listed below the table.

Table 5.

Vowel pronunciation according to ELF DN marking (The table does not apply to digraphs and sequences with R)

ELF Diacritic Notation		Pronunciation					Comments
Marking	Examples of Notation	ELF Default	AmE Typical	BrE Typical	Possible Variations	In Exceptions or Rare	
Grave accent (̀) (or without diacritic in stressed syllables ¹⁾)	⟨à⟩ or ⟨a⟩ ¹⁾	/æ/				/e/ ^{2a)}	Typically short monophthongs, full, stressed
	⟨è⟩ or ⟨e⟩ ¹⁾	/e/				/ɪ/ ^{2b)}	
	⟨ì, ÿ⟩ or ⟨i, y⟩ ¹⁾	/ɪ/					
	⟨ò⟩ or ⟨o⟩ ¹⁾	/ɑ/	/ɒ/	/ʌ/	/ʊ, ɪ/ ^{2c)}		
	⟨ù⟩ or ⟨u⟩ ¹⁾	/ʌ/				/ʊ, ɪ, e/ ^{2d)}	
Without diacritic in unstressed syllables	⟨a⟩	/ə/	/ə/ ³⁾		/ɪ/ ³⁾	/æ/	Typically reduced or weak, not crucial for intelligibility
	⟨e⟩	/ə/	/ə, ɪ/ ³⁾			/e/	
	⟨i, y⟩	/ɪ/	/ɪ, ə, i/ ³⁾				
	⟨o⟩	/ə/	/ə/			/ɑ ɒ/	
	⟨u⟩	/ə/	/ə/ or /jə, jʊ/ ⁴⁾		/ʊ/ ⁵⁾	/ʌ/	
Acute accent (´)	⟨á⟩	/eɪ/					Diphthongs, usually stressed
	⟨é⟩						
	⟨í, ý⟩	/aɪ/					
	⟨ó⟩	/oʊ/	/əʊ/				
	⟨ú⟩	/ju:/			/u:/ ⁵⁾		
Macron (̄)	⟨ā⟩	/ɑ:/			/ɔ:/, /ɒ/ ⁶⁾		Monophthongs, typically long and stressed
	⟨ē⟩	/i:/					
	⟨ī, ÿ⟩						
	⟨ō⟩	/ɔ:/					
	⟨ū⟩	/u:/					
Breve (̆)	⟨ö⟩	/u:/					

Notes. Numbers correspond to references in Table 5.

- 1) In ELF Diacritic Notation, stress marking may be omitted where stress is predictable (e.g. in monosyllabic words and many disyllabic words with initial stress). In such cases vowels in stressed syllables should be pronounced as if marked with a grave accent.
- 2) Exceptions for short vowels in stressed syllables:
 - a) ⟨a⟩ → /e/: *many, any* (and derivatives such as *anyone*)
 - b) ⟨e⟩ → /ɪ/: *pretty, English*
 - c) ⟨o⟩ → /ɪ/: *women*; ⟨o⟩ → /ʊ/: *woman, wolf, bosom*
 - d) ⟨u⟩ → /ʊ/: *put, push, pull, full, bull, bush, bullet, bully, cushion, pudding, sugar*;
 ⟨u⟩ → /ɪ/: *busy, business*; ⟨u⟩ → /e/: *bury, burial*
- 3) Unstressed ⟨a, e⟩ may be realised as /ə/ or weak /ɪ/, and ⟨i, y⟩ as /ɪ, ə, i/. These distinctions are not marked because variation in unstressed syllables rarely affects intelligibility.
- 4) Unstressed ⟨u⟩ is pronounced /ə/ in closed syllables and /jə/ or /jʊ/ in open syllables.
- 5) Sequences /ju:, jʊ, jə/ after /d, t, s/ may undergo yod coalescence, e.g. ⟨dú, tú, sú⟩ → /dʒu:, tʃu:, ʃu:/; ⟨du, tu, su⟩ → /dʒʊ, dʒə, tʃʊ, tʃə, ʃʊ, ʃə/ in open unstressed syllables. Pronouncing /ju:, jʊ, jə/ without coalescence remains intelligible.
- 6) The spelling ⟨ā⟩ is often realised as /ɔ:/ or /ɒ/ after /w/ and before dark /l/. In ELF, it can generally be replaced with /ɑ:/ without risking unintelligibility.

Examples of words with vowels written in ELF Diacritic Notation are given in Table 6 in Section 4.

3.3.2 Digraphs and Vowel Sequences

Vowel digraphs should be read according to the letter marked with a diacritic. The unmarked letter should be ignored and not pronounced.

However, some digraphs without marking or with atypical marking must be read as follows:

- ⟨ee⟩ → /ɪ/, ending ⟨-ee⟩ → /i/ happy vowel)
- ⟨oo⟩ → /ʊ/, ⟨òo⟩ → /ʌ/, usually stressed
- ⟨oi, oy⟩ → /ɔɪ/
- ⟨ew⟩ → /ju:/, but /u:/ in sequences ⟨rew, lew, chew, jew⟩; exception: *sew* → /səʊ|soʊ/
- ⟨-eau, au⟩ → /əʊ|oʊ/ (rare)
- ⟨òū, òw, āū⟩ → /aʊ/
- ⟨ài, ày⟩ → /e/ (rare)

Other vowel digraphs without diacritics i.e. ⟨ai, ea, ei, ie, oa, ou, ui, eau⟩ should be pronounced as non stressed reduced /ə/ or weak /ɪ/.

Sequences involving the letter ⟨r⟩ (two pronunciation variants are given: BrE | AmE)

- ⟨èr, ìr, ÿr, òr, ùr, òur, èur, èar⟩ → /ɜ:(r)|ɜ/ (in stressed syllables even without diacritics)
- ⟨àr⟩ → /æ(r)|er/ (in stressed syllables even without diacritics)
- ⟨ár, áir, éar⟩ → /eə(r)|er/
- ⟨ēr, -ēre, ēar, ēer, ēir, īer⟩ → /ɪə(r)|ɪr/
- ⟨ír, ýr⟩ → /aɪə(r)|aɪr/
- ⟨-ūre, oūr⟩ → /ʊə(r)|ʊr/
- ⟨òūr⟩ → /aʊə(r)|aʊr/
- ⟨úr, eúr⟩ → /jʊə(r)|jʊr/
- ⟨ār⟩ → /ɑ:(r)|ɑ:r/, ⟨ōr⟩ → /ɔ:(r)|ɔ:r/

In ELF pronunciation the American variant is recommended.

Examples of words with vowel digraphs and sequences written using ELF Notation are shown in Table 7 in Section 4.

3.3.3. Consonants

Consonant pronunciation is considered last, as it is often conditioned by the surrounding vowels and vowel sequences.

Consonants marked with diacritics have the pronunciation specified below.

- ⟨g̃⟩ → /g/
- ⟨čh, č̃⟩ → /k/
- ⟨čh, č, ś⟩ → /ʃ/
- ⟨ḍ⟩ → /dʒ/, ⟨ṭ⟩ → /tʃ/

In cases where consonants are not marked, pronunciation follows general English consonant rules, including in particular:

- the pronunciation of digraphs ⟨ch, sh, ph, th⟩
- the pronunciation of ⟨c, g⟩ depending on context
- the pronunciation of the digraph ⟨gh⟩ depending on context
- silent consonants in initial clusters *kn-*, *wr-*, *gn-*, *ps-*, *pn-* and in final clusters *-mb*, *-mn*
- voicing of consonants in certain contexts
- palatalisation (i.e. realisation as /j, ʒ, tʃ/) in sequences ⟨ciV, siV, tiV⟩
- palatalisation related to yod coalescence in sequences ⟨tu, du, su⟩

As regards yod coalescence, dialect differences occur between BrE and AmE. When the correct pronunciation is uncertain, ELF recommends pronunciation without yod coalescence, which should remain intelligible. Examples of words with ambiguous or atypical consonant pronunciation written in ELF Notation are shown in Table 8 in Section 4.

3.3.4. Syllable Stress

Accurate pronunciation of vowels in stressed syllables is key to intelligibility. In ELF, incorrect stress alone does not prevent understanding, provided all vowels that should be stressed are pronounced correctly and retain their full quality.

In ELF Diacritic Notation, in the vast majority of cases, a diacritic placed over a vowel (except dieresis) indicates the stressed syllable. Therefore, vowels marked with such diacritics should be pronounced clearly and without reduction. However, a diacritic does not always indicate stress. Diacritics may also be omitted in one- and two-syllable words.

Stress can be determined more precisely by combining diacritic interpretation with general stress rules:

- Grave accent (`) – directly indicates a stressed vowel.
- Macron or breve (ˉ / ˘) – long monophthongs are almost always stressed, with rare exceptions occurring particularly in final syllables.
- Acute accent (´) – diphthongs are usually stressed, but may be unstressed particularly in the final syllable.
 - Vowel digraphs ⟨oo, ee, ew, oi, oy⟩ (without diacritics) representing phonemes /ʊ, ɪ, ju:, u:, ɔɪ/ are usually stressed.
 - Adjacent syllables rarely both carry stress – if neighboring syllables have diacritics, the diphthong or long monophthong may remain unstressed (e.g., *rheūmàtic*).
 - Two-syllable words without diacritics – stress is assumed on the first syllable.
 - Long, multi-syllable, or compound words – primary and secondary stress often occur. Primary stress is often on the second element (e.g., *èlemèntary*), but in compounds of two words it usually falls on the first element (*blàckbōard, grēenhòūse, newspáper, schöoltēacher, týpewriter*).

4. Examples of Using ELF Diacritic Notation

Tables 6–8 present examples of words written in ELF Diacritic Notation with explanatory notes. Table 6 illustrates vowel marking and pronunciation, Table 7 vowel digraphs, and Table 8 consonant marking. The lists cover a wide range of spelling–pronunciation combinations, including irregular and rare cases, demonstrating the effectiveness of the system.

Table 6.

Examples of Words with Vowels and Vowel-r Sequences in ELF Notation

	Diacritic Notation	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation	BrE/AmE pronounc.	Default ELF Pron., Remarks
acute accent (´) - diphthongs	á	náme, creátor, vácátion	/eɪ/	
	ár, -áre	párent, sháring, cáre	/eə(r) er/	/er/
	é	bàllét, úkuléle, càfé, étúde	/eɪ/	rare
	ó	ópen, sófa	/əʊ oʊ/	/oʊ/
	ú	úse, únit, músic, valúe	/ju:/	
	úr, -úre	fúry, cúrious, Eúrope, cúre, endúre	jʊə(r), jɔr/	/jɔr /
	í	fíne, clímb, líe, supplíer, scíence	/aɪ/	
	ý	ský, replý, dený, supplý		
	-íre, -ýre írV, ýrV	fíre, týre pírate, írony, pýrománia, fíring	/aɪə(r) aɪr/	/aɪr/

	Diacritic Notation	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation	BrE/AmE pronounc.	Default ELF Pron./Remarks	
Macron (¯) - full long monophthongs	ā	fāther, cār, āria, wāter, cāll, whāt, wās, wānt, wāsh, sālt, ālter	/ɑ:/ (/ɔ:/, /ɒ/)	/ɑ:/	
	ē	prócēdure, thēater	/i:/		
	ēr, -ēre	hēró, pēriod, sincēre	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	/ɪr/	
	ī, ŷ	māchīne, mosquītó	/i:/		
	ō	mōre, bōrn	/ɔ:/		
	ū	rūle, Jūne	/u:/		
	-ūre	lūre, assūre	/ʊə(r) ʊr/	/ʊr /	
Breve (˘)	ö, ȳ	möve, pröve, löse	/u:/		
Grave accent (`) or not marked in stressed syllable	à, a	fà mily, cat, accent, massive,	/æ/		
		many, any	/e/	exceptions	
	àr, a àrr, arr	càravan, màrathon, harass,	/æ(r) er/	/er/	
		arrów, càrry			
	è, e	cèlebráte, bed, lemon, extra, wedding	/e/		
	ò, o	mònastery hot, profit, monster	/ɒ ɑ/	/ɑ/	
		love, come, son	/ʌ/		
		wolf, woman / women	/ʊ/, /ɪ/	exceptions	
	ù, u	sun, jump,	/ʌ/		
		pùsh-button, pùllóver, pull	/ʊ/	exceptions	
		bùsiness, busy	/ɪ/	exceptions	
	ì, i ÿ, y	big, milk, simple, limit, visibility, amphibia, ambivalent	strong /ɪ/		
		sýstemàtic, sýllable, system, myth			
èr, (er stress.) ìr, (ir) ÿr, (yr) òr, (or) ùr, (ur)	pèrmanent, therm	/ɜ: ɜ/	/ɜ:/ only in R-closed stressed syllables		
	vìrtual, bìrdwātcher, bird				
	myrrh, myrtle, mÿrmecòlogy				
	word				
	fùrniture, fur, nurse				
Not marked in unstressed syllable	a	banàna, dàta, dollar, paráde	/ə/,	/ə/	
		amphibia, ambivalent	(exc./æ/)		
		còurage, pàlace	weak /ɪ/		
	e	cèlebráte, òpera, tèacher	/ə/,	/ə/	
		bènefit	/ɪ/weak		
		áthèist, creáte, reènter,	/i/		
	o	lemon, májor, doctor, gallon	/ə/	/ə/	
	u	in closed syllable	syrup, circus, sulfur, succèss	/ə/	/ə/
		in open syllable	dòcument, règular, rèfugēe, àctual, èducáte, figure, minute	/jə, jʊ, ə, (ɪ) /	/jə, jʊ/
	i	àctivity, taxi, bikíni (happy v.) tīāra, mediēval (hiatuses)	/i/	/ɪ/	
		limit, mèdicine,	/ɪ/weak		
		fà mily, original pòssible, hòrrible, àctivity, vísibility, pòsitive, pencil, fossil, civil	/ə/		
	y	happy, fà mily, (happy v.)	/i/	/ɪ/	
mythòlogy pòlysylàbic,		/ɪ/weak			
anàlysis, satyr, martyr		/ə/,			

Table 7.

Examples of Vowel Digraphs and Their R-Extended Sequences in ELF Notation

Sequences pronounced as Vowels or Diphthongs					Hiatuses and Exceptions
Notation		BrE/AmE Pronounc.	Comments	Examples	
ai	ái	/eɪ/	stressed or unstressed	detáil(v), main, ráinbàrrel	
	áy			dětáil(n), máintáin, dáy, anywáy,	
	áir	/eə(r) er/		fair, aircraft, áirbōarder	
	àì àý	/e/	atypical marking	sàid, agàin (or agáin), plàid, sàys	
	-ain	/-ən, -ɪn/	non-str. endings -ain	certain, curtain, captain, mòuntain,	
ea	ēa	/i:/	dominant pron. ~60%	ēat, sēa, tēacher	hiat.: reàlity, reàct rēārm crēāte thēātre, ídēä, àrēä
	ēar	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	breaking before /r/ (BrE)	clēar, wēary	
	eār	/ɑ:/		heārt	
	éa	/eɪ/		gréat, bréak	
	éar	/eə(r) er/		béar, swéar	
	èa	/e/		hèad, brèad, mèadow	
	èar	/ɜ:/	R-closed str. syl.	pèarl, lèarn, èarnestly	
	ea	/ə/		ócean, sergeant	
ee	ēe	/i:/	dominant pron.	slēep, quēen, bìrdsēed	hiat.: reènter
	ēer	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	breaking before /r/ (BrE)	enginēer, chēery, bēer	
	ee	/ɪ/	rare, no diacritic	breeches, been,	
	-ee	/i/	unstr. ending, happy vowel	coffee, committee	
ei ey	éi éy	/eɪ/	dominant pron.	wéight gréy, whéy,	hiat.: rēinstāl áthēist déity
	ēi ēy	/i:/		recēive, cēiling kēy, gēyser	
	ēir	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	exceptions	wēird	
	éir	/eə(r) er/	exceptions	héir, théir	
	eý	/aɪ/		eýe, geýser (US)	
	-ey	/i/	unstr. happy vowel,	money	
	èi	/e/	rare	lèisure, hèifer,	
ei	/ɪ, ə/	unstressed, weak or reduced	foreign, forfeit		
ie	īe	/i:/	dom. pron. > 50%	fīeld, bēlieve, thīef	hiat.: mediēval clíent quíet
	íe, ýe	/aɪ/		líe, fríed, rýe	
	ìe	/ɪ/	rare	sìeve	
	īer	/ɪə(r) ɪr/	rare	pīerce, tīer, bīer, fīerce	
	ìè	/e/	only exceptions	friènd	
	ie	/ɪ, ə/	unstressed, weak or reduced	ancient, kerchief	
	-ie(d/s)	/i/	ending, happy vowel	mōvie, cookie(s), carried	
oa	óa	/əʊ oʊ/	dominant pron.	bóat, cóat, róad	hiat.: óásis còaguláte prótozóa
	ōa	/ɔ:/	rare	bōard, brōad	
	oa	/ə/	unstressed, reduced	cùpboard	
oe	óe	/əʊ oʊ/	dominant	tóe	exc. does, phoēnix
	öe	/u:/		shöe(s)	

Sequences pronounced as Vowels or Diphtongs					Hiatuses and Exceptions
Notation		Pronounc.	Comments	Examples	
oi	oi oy	/ɔɪ/	stressed or unstressed no diacritic	choice, boil, voice boy, cònvoy, royal,	hiat.: <i>cóincidence</i> <i>sólóist,</i> <i>čhǒír</i>
	oi	/ə/ /wɑː/,	exceptions, French origin no diacritic	tórtois, cònnaisseùr, mèmoire	
oo	õo	/uː/	dominant pron. ~60%	mõon, fõod, kàngarõo	hiat.: <i>zòòlogy,</i> <i>còòperate</i>
	oo	/ʊ/	~30%, no diacritic	book, look, foot	
	õo	/ɔː/		dõor, flõor, mõor	
	òo	/ʌ/ (~ b ɑ/)	exceptions	blòod, flòod	
	óo	/əʊ oʊ/	exceptions	bróoch	
ou ow	óu ów	/əʊ oʊ/		āłthóugh snów, lów	exc. /ɒ ɑ/ - <i>knòwledge</i>
	oū	/uː/		throūgh	
	oūr	/ʊə(r) ʊr/		toūrist, coūrier	
	òu	/ɒ ɑ/		còugh	
	où	/ʌ/		yoùng, coùple, toùgh	
	òw òū	/aʊ/	atypical marking	cròwn, flòwer abòüt, pròüd,	
	òūr	/aʊə(r) aʊr/		flòūr, hòūrly	
	ōu	/ɔː/		thòught,	
	ōur	/ɔː(r)/		fōur	
	òur	/ɜː/	R-closed str. syl. (rare)	jòurney	
	ou	/ə/	non-str. endings -ous, -our	fámous, colour	
	au aw	āw āu	/ɔː~ɒ~ɑː/	pron. depending on dialect Intelligible default ELF: /ɑː/	
āu or àu		/ɑː/ or /æ/		āunt, lāugh àunt, làugh	
áu,		/eɪ/	exceptions	gáuge	
āū,		/aʊ/	atypical marking	sāuerkrāūt,	
au		/oʊ əʊ/	no diacritic, exception	gauche	
ue	-úe, úe	/juː/		vàlúe, ārgúe, Túesday	hiat.: <i>fúèl, dūèt</i> <i>crūèl, sūèt</i>
	-ūe	/uː/		blūe	
	ué	/weɪ/	rare	suéde	
ui	úi	/juː/		súit	hiat.: <i>rūīn,</i> <i>īntuītion</i> exc. /gʊɪ/- <i>pènguīn,</i> <i>ànguīsh</i>
	ūi	/uː/		frūit, crūise	
	uí, uý	/aɪ/		guíde, buý	
	uì	/ɪ/ strong		buìld, guìlty,	
	ui	weak /ɪ/	unstressed	guitār, circúit, bìscuit	
eu	eū	/uː/	rare	rheūmàtic, sleūth	hiat.: <i>reúse</i> <i>músēum</i> exc.: /ɜː/ - <i>massèuse</i> /ɔɪ/ - <i>Freud</i>
	eú	/juː/	typical initial eu- /juː/	eúphoric, feúd	
	eúr	/jʊə(r) jʊr/		Eúrope	
	-èur	/ɜː/	in stress. endings -èur	cònnaisseùr, massèur	
	-eur	/ə/	in non-str. endings -eur	àmateur	
ew	ew	/juː/	typical, no diacritic	few, ewe, steward	
	ew	/uː/	after ⟨ch, j, l, r⟩	crew, jewel, chew, lewd	
	ew	/əʊ oʊ/	exceptions	sew, sewing	
eau	eaú	/juː/	French origin	beaúty	
	eāu	/ɒ ɑ/		búreāucracy	
	-eau	/əʊ oʊ/	no diacritic, French origin	beau, búreau, plateau	
	eau	/ə/		búreaucrat	

Table 8.*Examples of Words with Ambiguous or Atypical Consonant Pronunciation in ELF Notation*

Notation	Pron. IPA	Typical Context, Notes,	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation (Some examples also in IPA notation)
g	/g/	typical, except below	gráve, good
	/dʒ/	typical before e, i, y	gentle, ginger, coùrage, Ēgypt
ġ	/g/	irregular before e, i, y mainly Germanic, Greek origin	ġirl, ġive, ġift, ġeese, tġger, ġecko, ġeyser, ġigabyte, ġynecology
gh	/g/	typical before vowel	ghóst, ghāstly, gherkin, ghattó, spaghètti
	mute	before consonant or at the end	thóugh, dóugh, ālthóugh, thóught, slāughter (exc. <i>Baghdad</i>)
	/f/	exceptions	lāugh, lāughter, coūgh, tōugh
c	/k/	typical, except below	cat, coffee, cōre, clóse, lecture, (exc.: <i>caesúra, caesium/cēsium, facāde/façāde</i>)
	/s/	before e, i, y	cēiling, circus. cíder, cýan, (exc.: <i>sceptic/skeptíc, Celtic /'keltɪk, 'seltɪk/</i>)
	/ʃ/	exceptions, optional ⟨ć⟩	ócean
ck	/k/	typical	back, socket
ch ch ch	/tʃ/	typical	chief, much, cherry
	/k/	scientific, Greek origin	sčhool, čhèmisty, čháos, ārchitect
	/ʃ/	French origin, borrowings	čef, mačhine, bróchure
ci	/ʃ/	seq. ⟨ciV⟩: endings -cial, -cian - cious, -cient	special, sócial, rácial, spácious, grácious, ancient, physician
	/si/	in hiatus, optionally marked by (¨)	pronùnciátiön, annùnciáte, calciüm
s	/s/	typical, except below	snów, some
	/z/	usually between vowels (not double ss)	ēasy, busy, excúse(v), (but <i>massive, fossil, lesson</i> except <i>dessèrt</i>)
	/ʃ, ʒ/	endings -ssure, -sure, other rare, optionally marked ⟨ś⟩	prèssure, lèisure, mèasure, clósure śugar, śüre
si	/ʃ/	endings: -Csiön, -ssion, -ssia(n)	version, pension, passion, Russia(n),
	/ʒ/	endings: -Vsiön, -Vsia(n)	vision, fúsiön, decisiön, Ásian
	/si, zi/	in hiatus, optionally marked by (¨)	endings -sius, -sium: Celsiüs, cēsium
d	/d/	typical	duck
	/dʒ/	endings -dure, and exceptions optionally marked by caron ⟨ď⟩	prócēdure, soldġier, èďucáte
	/d, dj, dʒ/	before u in open syl. ⟨du, dū, dú⟩ pronounc. depends on the dialect	dūal, dúne, dūring
t	/t/	typical	task
	/tʃ/	endings -ture, and some exceptions optionally marked by caron ⟨ť⟩	fűrniture, náture, lecture àctűal, riűual
	/t, tj, tʃ/	before u in open syl. ⟨tu, tū, tú⟩ pronounc. depends on the dialect	Túesdáy, tútor
ti	/tʃ/	seq. ⟨stiV⟩: e.g., -stion, -stian	question, Christian,
	/ʃ/	seq., ⟨tiV⟩: endings e.g., -tion, -tial, -tious, -tient, -tian, -tia, -tiáte, -tiátion, -tiáble, and other	nátion, action, spátial, pārtial, inítial, ostentátious, pátient, Egyptian, militia, inítiáte, negótiátion, negótiáble, rátió
	/ti-/	hiatuses, (optionally marked by dieresis),	bástiön, celéstial, tiāra, etiòlogy, stròntiüm, pàtió
th	/θ/	typical, except below	myth, think, thumb
	/ð/	usually between vowels	mother, fāther, bother (but <i>ēther, āuthor, method</i>)

Notation	Pron. IPA	Typical Context, Notes,	Examples Written Using ELF Diacritic Notation
x	/ks/	typical, except below	box, wax, expànd
	/kʃ/	bef. u in op. syl., endings, -xure, -xury, -xual, -xious, -xion, -xiety	lùxury /'lʌkʃəri/, sèxual, anxious, complèxion
	/gz/,	prefix ex- before vowel	exàmine, èxecúte, exhāust
	/z/	at the word beginning	xýlophóne, xenon, xènophóbia
qu	/kw/	typical	quíet, liquid
	/k/	endings -que, borrowings	únique, conquer, mosquító
ng	/ŋ/	in endings or before cons.	ring, long
	/ŋg/	if before vowel	longer
nk, nx	/ŋk/		bank, link, anxious
g, j, z	/ʒ/	exceptions, French origin	prestíge, mirāge, bijou àzure, sēizure
cz	/tʃ/,	exceptions	Czech, czardaś,
	/z/		czar

5. Ambiguities and Possible Extensions of the Diacritic Notation

5.1. Advantages and Limitations of ELF Diacritic Notation

In the author's view, the ELF Diacritic Notation presented here should be sufficient for intelligibility, provided the reader is familiar with general rules of English orthography and pronunciation. A further advantage is that, in practice, the notation varies only minimally between British and American English. Any differences depend on whether the editor of a diacritically marked text follows one variety or the other, but they are limited to relatively few words with substantial cross-dialectal variation.

However, what constitutes an advantage from one perspective may also be seen as a limitation from another. A simplified pronunciation notation of this kind is not fully sufficient for learners who expect an explicit representation of the standard pronunciation of one of the major reference varieties, namely British or American English.

In particular, the following ambiguities and limitations occur in the notation:

Vowels

- ⟨ā⟩ represents /ɑ:/, which is usually intelligible in ELF, but in dialectal variations may occasionally correspond to /ɔ:/ or /ɒ/.
- The grave accent marks stress and only partially indicates the phonemic value of the vowel.
- Unstressed vowels, which are not crucial for intelligibility, are left unmarked in ELF DN, making their phonemic value ambiguous.

Consonants

The notation does not always indicate:

- palatalised realisations of ⟨c, s, t, d⟩ as /j, ʒ, tʃ, dʒ/ (only optional and limited in extent)
- voiced realisations of ⟨s, th, x⟩ as /z, ð, gz/
- rare realisations of ⟨g, j, z⟩ as /ʒ/

Further limitations

- Silent letters are not indicated.
- Word stress is marked, but ambiguities occur; primary and secondary stress are not distinguished.

- The system does not account for the pronunciation of loanwords, proper names, surnames, or orthographically exceptional items (e.g., *one, quay, colonel, sergeant, burial*).

These ambiguities and limitations are inherent in a system designed primarily for functional intelligibility rather than for exhaustive phonemic precision. Within the ELF framework, they should not normally result in communicative breakdown, provided that users are familiar with general English orthographic conventions and main exceptions.

5.2. Possible Extensions of the Diacritic Notation

The diacritic system is scalable, and additional marks can be introduced to reduce or eliminate ambiguities. However, introducing additional marks increases the differences in notation between AmE and BrE, making the term *ELF Diacritic Notation* less appropriate. Nevertheless, the system itself retains its universal character.

Possible extensions to ELF DN and their proposed names:

1) English Learner's Diacritic Notation

Additional character proposals to distinguish full vowel and consonant values:

- Disambiguation of ⟨ā⟩ → /ɑ:/, ⟨ɔ:/, ⟨ɒ/ (⟨ā⟩ → /ɑ:/ only)
 - Strut vowel /ʌ/ distinction: additional characters ⟨ô, û⟩ → /ʌ/
 - Irregular consonant pronunciation marking (standard, not optional): ⟨ś, ć⟩ → /ʃ/, ⟨d'⟩ → /dʒ/, ⟨t'⟩ → /tʃ/, ⟨ǰ, ǰ', ǰ'⟩ → /ʒ/
 - Hiatus marking by dieresis — standard, not optional

This supplemented notation allows for recording correct pronunciation consistent with RP or GA. The phonemic value of some characters remains context-dependent, similar to ELF Diacritic Notation. Adding diacritics to vowels does not make the notation denser, as the marks ⟨°, ^, ^⟩ replace the ambiguous ⟨¯, `⟩. Additional consonant characters are used only to indicate irregular cases of pronunciation, which are rare. This notation could be proposed for teaching texts for students at levels A2–B1.

2) Extended English Learner's Diacritic Notation.

This extension introduces additional characters to provide broader phoneme disambiguation:

- Vowels distinctions: additional characters ⟨ā, ē, ô, û⟩ → /ɪ, i/, ⟨û⟩ → /jə, jʊ/, ⟨û⟩ → /ɔ:/
- Context-independent palatalisation marking: ⟨ś, ć, ć'⟩ → /ʃ/, ⟨ǰ'⟩ → /kʃ/, ⟨d'⟩ → /dʒ/, ⟨t'⟩ → /tʃ/
- Additional character for digraph ⟨ǰh⟩ → /f/
- Voiced pronunciation marking: ⟨ś, ǰ⟩ → /z/, ⟨ś'⟩ → /ʒ/, ⟨th'⟩ → /ð/, ⟨x'⟩ → /gz/
- Breaking before /r/ marking (in BrE): ⟨r̄⟩ → /ə(r)/
- Silent (mute) sounds marking with X above: ⟨ë, ĝ, ĥ, k̄, ñ, ř'⟩ etc.

This set of characters allows the recording of all standard English phonemes. The phonemic value of some characters remains context-dependent, though to a lesser extent than in previous notations. Correct pronunciation requires knowledge of only the basic rules and a few exceptions. The notation becomes denser and less transparent, but it may be useful for teaching texts aimed at beginners (A1).

3) English Dictionary Diacritic Notation.

This notation introduces additional characters to provide accuracy comparable to IPA phonemic transcription:

- Vowel characters: ⟨ä⟩ → /e/, ⟨ö⟩ → /ʊ/; ⟨ï, ë⟩ → neutralized or happy /i/; ⟨ü⟩ → weak /jʊ/; ⟨ê, î⟩ → /ɐ | ə/ (in some words of French origin)
- Additional character dotless l: ⟨l̄⟩ → /ə/; all ⟨a, e, i, o, u, y⟩ → /ə/, and all ⟨ā, ē, i, ô, û, ÿ⟩ → /ɪ/

- Nurse vowel context-independent dedicated marking: ⟨è, ì, ÿ, ò, ù⟩ → /ɜ:|ə/
- Context-independent consonant marking: ⟨ç⟩ → /s/, ⟨ğ⟩ → /dʒ/
- Primary stress marking: dot below, e.g. ⟨à, à̇⟩

With this notation, the phonemic value of each character is context-independent. It enables the transcription of almost any word—including lexical exceptions—with a precision approaching that of IPA phonemic notation. Only extremely irregular spellings, such as some borrowings or proper names, may pose difficulties. This system can be used in dictionaries, allowing spelling and pronunciation to be recorded presented in a uniform notation, which facilitates learning both aspects simultaneously.

6. Summary

In order to demonstrate the use of ELF Diacritic Notation in practice, this summary is marked with diacritics according to the rules described in the article.

The article presents a new diacritic-based method for recording pronunciation, whose key feature is that, after removing the diacritics, the notation aligns with standard spelling. The basic ELF Diacritic Notation presented here achieves accuracy that is usually sufficient for intelligibility in international communication according to the principles of the Lingua Franca Core (LFC). Thanks to diacritics, the system represents pronunciation almost as predictably as more regular alphabetic orthographies, making it intuitive for readers familiar with standard spelling conventions.

ELF Diacritic Notation is primarily intended for use between non-native speakers, supporting intelligible reading in contexts such as international business or technical meetings. If widely adopted, it could serve as a reference framework for simplified, globally intelligible pronunciation in English as a Lingua Franca.

The author's practical experience suggests that, particularly through the explicit marking of stress and vowel quality, the use of ELF DN can help disrupt automatic pronunciation habits that learners transfer from their first language, helping them read English more consciously and clearly. This is especially important in formal oral presentations.

The notation system is scalable and can be extended with additional diacritic marks and characters to represent pronunciation with greater precision. Such extensions may increase differences in this notation between British and American English, but the system retains its universal character and still can be applied consistently across dialects. This makes the system potentially useful in English language teaching, helping students master both spelling and pronunciation through a unified “two-in-one” notation suitable for didactic texts. It is particularly beneficial for independent learners who rely more on visual memory, though it also supports correct articulation for other students.

The most extended version of the method (Dictionary Diacritic Notation) while maintaining standard spelling, is intended to be comparable in precision with the phonemic IPA Notation and to be effective even for words with very irregular spelling.

These proposals are not the only possible approach to addressing this issue and may be further refined. Feedback from teachers, learners, and other researchers is welcomed, as this work is intended as a foundation for further research.

In particular, the author—himself an average non-native user of English—wishes to encourage researchers working on English as a Lingua Franca to explore this area. In his view, the contemporary globalised and multilingual world would benefit from research into functionally oriented models of simplified, intelligibility-based English pronunciation. The ELF Diacritic Notation, or its improved

versions, may serve as one practical tool supporting such efforts. Future work may explore its application in ELF pedagogy, English language teaching, and independent learning contexts.

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